

Spectral Studies of Polymeric Metal Complexes with Schiff Bases of Terephthalaldehyde and Hydrazides

P. L. MAURYA*, C. P. DUBE and B. V. AGARWALA*

Chemical Laboratories, University of Allahabad, Allahabad-211 002

Polymerization reactions involving the formation of Schiff base metal complexes by condensation have been described. The Schiff bases formed are terephthalaldehyde bis-(benzoic acid hydrazone) (TBH) and terephthalaldehyde bis-(nicotinic acid hydrazone) (TNH). The IR spectra indicate that chelation occurs through their enolic form. Both hydrazones act as tetradentate ligands and a polymeric structure is proposed for 1:1 complexes. All complexes except Zn(II) are paramagnetic which along with calculated values of ligand field parameters, ν_2/ν_1 , $10 Dq$, B' , β and β' , obtained from electronic spectral data support an octahedral geometry.

METAL complexes¹⁻⁵ of Schiff bases of hydrazides with aldehydes and ketones have been of special interest in recent years, particularly in the context of therapeutic value of hydrazide and hydrazone. The coordination occurs both in keto⁵⁻⁶ as well as enolic form^{3,4} of the ligands with the metal ions. Larsen *et al.*^{7,8} have made an extensive study on molecular and electronic structure in metal complexes with Schiff bases of β -diketones and diamines by absorption and circular dichroism spectra. The results have been interpreted by means of molecular exciton theory to rationalize the observations on the dimeric Schiff bases. Formation of oxygen bridged bi- and trinuclear complexes have also been described in a review by Sinn and Harris⁹.

The present paper describes the synthesis and characterisation of Schiff bases viz., terephthalaldehyde bis-(benzoic acid hydrazone) (TBH) and terephthalaldehyde bis-(nicotinic acid hydrazone) (TNH) and their complexes with Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II). The results are discussed with the aid of infrared and electronic spectra and magnetic and thermal data. These complexes are similar to several coordination polymers of Schiff bases with other terephthalaldehyde derivatives, which had been initiated by Prof. A. K. Dey¹⁰⁻¹².

Experimental

Materials :

Terephthalaldehyde (Koch Light), and nicotinic acid hydrazone and benzoic acid hydrazone were used to synthesize the Schiff bases. $Mn(CH_3COO)_2 \cdot 4H_2O$, $Cu(CH_3COO)_2 \cdot H_2O$, $Zn(CH_3COO)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ (all BDH, AnalaR), $Co(CH_3COO)_2 \cdot 4H_2O$ (Surabhai M.), $Ni(CH_3COO)_2 \cdot 4H_2O$ (Veb Laborchemie) were used and the solvents were of reagent grade.

Preparation of Schiff bases : Benzoic acid hydrazone (13.6 g ; 0.1 mol) or nicotinic acid hydrazone (13.7 g ; 0.1 mol) and terephthalaldehyde (6.7 g ; 0.05 mol) dissolved in ethanol were mixed and refluxed on a water bath for 2 hr. The precipi-

tated white crystalline solids were filtered, washed successively with water, ethanol, diethylether, and dried (yield ca 80%). The Schiff bases obtained are insoluble in water, ethanol, chloroform, benzene, acetone, toluene, xylene, but soluble in DMF and DMSO. Found : C, 72.3 ; H, 4.82 ; N, 16.05. Calcd. for $C_{22}H_{18}N_4O_2$; C, 71.35 ; H, 4.86 ; N, 15.14% and C, 64.32 ; H, 4.45 ; N, 22.94. Calcd. for $C_{20}H_{16}N_4O_2$; C, 64.51 ; H, 4.30 ; N, 22.58%.

Synthesis of Schiff base-metal complexes : TBH or TNH (0.1 mol) dissolved in DMF was gradually added to a solution of the metal salt (0.01 mol) in DMF- H_2O media. The mixture was refluxed at ca 120° for 2 to 3 hr as necessary and left overnight. The precipitated mass was filtered, washed with DMF, ethanol and ether and dried (yield 80-85%).

The complexes are air stable, powdery and insoluble in water and common organic solvents viz., ethanol, acetone, benzene, chloroform, nitrobenzene, THF, DMF and DMSO.

Analytical data : Microanalytical methods were used for the determination of carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen. The complexes were decomposed by fuming HNO_3 and the metal contents estimated titrimetrically against EDTA.

Magnetic susceptibility : The magnetic susceptibility of the complexes were determined at 298 K by Faraday's method.

Spectral studies : IR spectra were recorded on Beckman Infrared spectrophotometer using KBr pellets in the range of 4000-400 cm^{-1} , DRS were obtained in the range 200-1000 nm using Carl-Zeiss spectrophotometer VSU-2.

Thermogravimetry : TG was done by heating the complexes upto 800° at a rate of 10° min^{-1} in air.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data of the complexes (Table 1) agree with the general formula $(ML_2H_2O)_n$ where

*Present address : Leningrad, U.S.S.R.

M=Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), or Zn(II),
L=C₂₂H₁₆N₄O₂ or C₂₀H₁₄N₆O₄.

TABLE 1—COLOUR AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Complex	Colour	Analyses %			
		Found (Calcd.)			
		M	C	H	N
MnL.2H ₂ O	Brown	11.64 (11.97)	56.92 (57.52)	4.32 (4.35)	13.04 (12.20)
CoL.2H ₂ O	Reddish brown	12.26 (12.73)	57.42 (57.02)	4.30 (4.32)	12.82 (12.09)
NiL.2H ₂ O	Greenish yellow	12.16 (12.68)	56.96 (57.05)	4.42 (4.32)	12.69 (12.10)
CuL.2H ₂ O	Brown	13.05 (13.58)	56.92 (56.46)	4.35 (4.27)	12.02 (11.97)
ZnL.2H ₂ O	Yellow	13.21 (13.92)	56.52 (56.24)	4.48 (4.26)	12.43 (11.93)
MnL'.2H ₂ O	Brown	11.54 (11.91)	52.84 (52.02)	3.86 (3.90)	18.94 (18.22)
CoL'.2H ₂ O	Brown	12.42 (12.67)	51.48 (51.61)	3.92 (3.87)	18.76 (18.06)
NiL'.2H ₂ O	Yellow	12.16 (12.63)	52.04 (51.64)	3.82 (3.87)	18.99 (18.06)
CuL'.2H ₂ O	Brown	13.16 (13.53)	51.41 (51.11)	3.94 (3.83)	17.81 (17.88)
ZnL'.2H ₂ O	Yellow	13.34 (13.86)	51.02 (50.91)	3.89 (3.81)	17.95 (17.82)

L=C₂₂H₁₆N₄O₂, L'=C₂₀H₁₄N₆O₄

characteristic bands near 3250, 1650, 1300, 750 and 670 assigned to N-H stretching, C=O stretching, N-H in-plane bending, C=O in-plane deformation and C=O out-of-plane deformation, respectively¹⁸. The bands near 1630 and 1600 are assigned to C=N and C=C stretching, respectively. The bands at 1485 and 1050 in TNH are due to pyridine ring

TABLE 3B—IR SPECTRA* OF TNH AND ITS COMPLEXES

TNH	Mn(II)	Co(II)	Ni(II)	Cu(II)	Zn(II)	Assignment
...	3500	3505	3510	3500	3510	ν OH(H ₂ O)
3250	...	...	...	...	...	ν NH
1655	...	...	...	...	...	ν C=O
1630	1620	1620	1615	1615	1510	ν C=N
1600	1600	1610	1600	1610	1610	ν C=C and δ H ₂ O
...	1560	1565	1560	1560	1565	ν C=N-N=C
1485	1485	1480	1485	1485	1485	ν N=N-(pyridine)
1305	...	...	...	...	...	δ NH
...	1290	1285	1285	1290	1290	ν C-O
1050	1050	1050	1045	1050	1050	ν N=N-(pyridine)
910	920	925	925	930	930	ν N-N
750	...	...	...	...	...	C=O in-plane
670	...	...	...	...	...	C=O out-of-plane deformation
...	525	520	515	520	520	ν M-O
...	450	455	460	450	450	ν M-N

* Wave numbers are in cm⁻¹.

TABLE 2—MAGNETIC MOMENT, ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA AND LIGAND FIELD PARAMETERS OF TBH AND TNH* COMPLEXES

Complex with	Magnetic moment	Electronic spectra		ν_2/ν_1	10 D _q	B'	β	β^0	Geometry
		Band cm ⁻¹	Assignment						
Mn(II)	5.92 (5.80)	17500	⁶ A _{1g} → T _{1g} (G)	...	...	...	...	...	Octahedral
		21240	→ T _{2g} (G)						
		23450	→ E _g (G)						
		26520	→ T _{2g} (D)						
		28750	→ E _g (D)						
Co(II)	4.89 (4.91)	10200	⁴ T _{1g} → ⁴ T _{2g} (F)	2.1 (2.1)	11150 (11450)	893 (893)	0.919 (0.920)	800 (8.00)	Octahedral
		21350	→ ⁴ A _{2g} (F)						
		22300	→ ⁴ T _{1g} (P)						
		10150	⁶ A _{2g} → ⁶ T _{2g} (F)						
		15200	→ ⁶ T _{1g} (F)						
Ni(II)	2.96 (3.02)	27750	→ ⁶ T _{1g} (P)	1.5 (1.5)	10150 (10200)	922 (911)	0.873 (0.863)	12.68 (13.65)	Octahedral
		10100	⁸ B _{1g} → ⁸ A _{1g}						
		11150	→ ⁸ B _{2g}						
Cu(II)	1.95 (1.98)	15200	→ ² E _g	...	10100 (10000)	...	...	...	Octahedral

* Values within the parentheses are for TNH complexes.

TABLE 3A—IR SPECTRA* OF TBH AND ITS COMPLEXES

TBH	Mn(II)	Co(II)	Ni(II)	Cu(II)	Zn(II)	Assignment
...	3510	3500	3510	3510	3500	ν OH(H ₂ O)
3250	...	...	...	...	...	ν NH
1650	...	...	...	...	...	ν C=O
1630	1615	1620	1620	1620	1620	ν C=N
1600	1610	1600	1600	1610	1610	δ (H ₂ O) + ν C=C
...	1570	1560	1560	1560	1565	ν C=N-N=C
1300	...	...	...	...	...	δ NH
...	1290	1290	1285	1290	1290	ν C-O
915	935	935	940	940	935	ν N-N
750	...	...	...	...	...	C=O in-plane
670	...	...	...	...	...	C=O out-of-plane deformation
...	520	520	510	510	520	ν M-O
450	450	460	460	450	455	ν M-N

* Wave numbers are in cm⁻¹.

The ir spectra (Tables 3A and 3B, wave numbers expressed in cm⁻¹) of TBH and TNH show chara-

nitrogen. All these bands in the spectra of TBH and TNH indicate that these are present in keto form, and the proposed structures I and II for the Schiff bases are as follows :

I. TBH

II. TNH

However, the chelation occurs through enolic form which finds support from the fact that (i) C=O stretching bands disappear and (ii) new bands

appear near 1570-50 and 1290-85 which may be assigned to C=N-N=C stretching and C-O stretching at C-O-M site, respectively. The involvement of azomethine nitrogens for coordination is indicated by (i) a negative shift in the stretching frequency of C=N group and (ii) a positive shift in the stretching vibrations of N-N group¹⁴ in the spectra of the complexes. Coordination through oxygen and nitrogen are further supported by the occurrence of new bands at ~520-510 and ~460-450 which may be assigned to M-O and M-N stretching frequencies, respectively. The ring nitrogens in the case of TNH do not take part in coordination as the bands observed at 1485 and 1050 due to ν N=N-(pyridine) remain unchanged on chelation.

Thus, both the Schiff bases act as tetradentate ligands as each metal ion is coordinated with two nitrogen and two oxygen atoms. Coordination polymerization takes place since all the four donors in one ligand molecule can not coordinate to the same metal ion due to steric factors. Two water molecules are attached to satisfy the coordination number. The presence of water molecule is indicated by the observance of strong bands at 3500 and 1600 in the ir spectra which may be assigned to ν OH and δ H₂O, respectively. The percentage weight loss observed between 100-200° by TG analysis correspond to the elimination of 2 H₂O, thus supporting the above assumption.

III. TBH complexes

Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) complexes are paramagnetic and the magnetic moment values at 298 K are found to be: 5.92, 4.89, 2.96, 1.95 and 5.90, 4.91, 3.02 and 1.98 B.M. for the two series of complexes, respectively. Various ligand field parameters viz., ν_8/ν_1 , $10 D_q$, B' , β and β^0 have

been calculated (Table 2) from electronic spectral data. Both these data show octahedral geometry of the complexes¹⁹⁻²⁰. The geometry, composition, insolubility and high thermal stability of the complexes indicate their polymeric nature^{1, 2, 21}.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi for awarding a Post-doctoral Fellowship to (P.L.M.).

References

1. I. I. GEORGESCU, D. CIOMARTAN, G. TEODORESCU, M. HLEVCA and M. ZAHARESU, *Riv. Roum. Chim.*, 1973, 18, 1195.
2. A. P. NARIMANIDZE, A. M. MAMULASHVILI and T. K. DZHASHIASHVILI, *Tr. Gruz. Politekh. Inst.*, 1975, 4, 34.
3. K. K. NARANG and A. AGARWAL, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1975, 13, 1072.
4. R. C. AGGARWAL, L. PRASAD and N. K. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1976, 14A, 181.
5. R. C. AGGARWAL and T. R. RAO, *Trans. Metal Chem.*, 1977, 2, 201; *Curr. Sci.*, 1977, 46, 625.
6. K. K. KHAKIMOV, A. A. SHABILALOV and M. A. AZIZOV, *Russ. J. Inorg. Chem.*, 1970, 15, 1022.
7. E. LARSEN, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1969, 23, 2158.
8. E. LARSEN and K. SCHAUMBERG, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1971, 25, 962.
9. E. SINN and C. M. HARRIS, *Coord. Chem. Revs.*, 1969, 4, 391.
10. P. L. MAURYA, B. V. AGARWALA and A. K. DEY, *Polymer Bull.*, 1979, 1, 631; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, 57, 275.
11. B. SINGH, V. BANERJIE, B. V. AGARWALA and A. K. DEY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, 57, 365.
12. B. SINGH, P. L. MAURYA, B. V. AGARWALA and A. K. DEY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, 58, 541.
13. T. MIYAZAWA, T. SHIMANOUCI and S. MIZUSHIMA, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1956, 24, 408; 1958, 29, 611.
14. P. A. GIGURE and I. D. LIN, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1952, 20, 136.
15. K. NAKAMOTO, "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Coordination Compounds", Wiley, New York, 1978.
16. J. W. STAUT, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1959, 31, 709.
17. A. B. P. LEVER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy". Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1968.
18. C. J. BALLHAUSEN, "Introduction to Ligand Field Theory", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1962.
19. R. S. DRAGO, "Physical Methods in Inorganic Chemistry", Reinhold, New York, 1965.
20. L. SACCONI, *Transition Metal Chemistry*, 1968, 4, 199.
21. P. L. MAURYA, B. V. AGARWALA and A. K. DEY, *Polymer Bull.*, 1980, 3, 253; *Makromol. Chem.*, 1982, 183, 511.